

Consistent Device Simulation Model Describing Perovskite Solar Cells in Steady-State, Transient and Frequency Domain

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1. Abstract

A variety of experiments on vacuum deposited methylammonium lead iodide perovskite solar cells is presented, including JV curves with different scan rates, light intensity dependent open-circuit voltage, impedance spectra, intensity-modulated photocurrent spectra (IMPS), transient photocurrents and transient voltage step responses. All these experimental data sets are successfully reproduced by a charge drift-diffusion simulation model incorporating mobile ions and charge traps using a single set of parameters. While previous modelling studies focused on a single experimental technique, we combine steady-state, transient and frequency-domain simulations and measurements. Our study is an important step towards quantitative simulation of perovskite solar cells leading to a deeper understanding of the physical effects in these materials. The analysis of the transient current upon voltage turn-on in the dark reveals that the charge injection properties of the interfaces are triggered by the accumulation of mobile ionic defects. We show that the current rise of voltage step experiments allow for conclusions about the recombination at the interface. Whether one or two mobile ionic species are used in the model, has only a minor influence on the observed effects.

A delayed current rise observed upon reversing the bias from +3V to -3V in the dark cannot be reproduced yet by our drift-diffusion model. We speculate that a reversible chemical reaction of mobile ions with the contact material may be the cause of this effect thus requiring a future model extension.

A parameter variation is performed in order to understand the performance limiting factors of the device under investigation.

Keywords: perovskite solar cells, hysteresis, mobile ions, traps, impedance spectroscopy, IMPS, transient photo-current, drift-diffusion modelling

2. Introduction

Perovskite solar cells are promising candidates as top cells in tandem architectures with crystalline silicon or CIGS as bottom cell. A record efficiency of 26.7% has been demonstrated with methylammonium lead iodide perovskite on top of a silicon solar cell with PERL structure ¹. Such perovskite-silicon tandem solar cells can potentially reach power conversion efficiencies beyond 30% ^{2,3}.

Organic-inorganic perovskites are electronic-ionic conductors, which is believed to be the reason for the observed JV curve hysteresis ⁴ and other intriguing effects like the extraordinarily high low-frequency capacitance under illumination ⁵. Thereby iodine vacancies can migrate and lead to a screening of the electric field ⁶⁻⁹. The exact physical operation mechanisms of perovskite solar cells remain however under debate.

The physical processes in these materials are often too complex to be understood by ad-hoc explanations or simple analytical formulas. Numerical simulations offer a deeper understanding of the underlying device physics. First charge drift-diffusion models incorporating mobile ions were presented by Van Reenen ¹⁰, Richardson ^{11,12} and Calado ¹³. In these models the JV curve is simulated with a transient solver in forward and reverse direction, reproducing the observed JV curve hysteresis. Similar models were applied to simulate transient voltage steps ¹⁴, open-circuit voltage transients ^{15,16}, transient photocurrents ¹⁷, capacitance-voltage ¹⁸ and impedance spectroscopy ¹⁸ as well as intensity-modulated photocurrent/photovoltage spectroscopy ¹⁶.

Despite the success of these models in qualitatively reproducing the observed effects, it remains under debate whether mobile ions are sufficient to describe the working mechanism of perovskite solar cells. All models presented so far were usually applied to simulate a single experiment. Conclusions from only one experiment can be error-prone as we show in the following paragraph. We would like to note that these models also neglect RC effects, playing an important role in transient or frequency-domain experiments, hereby complicating the direct quantitative comparison of simulated and measured data. Therefore this study, including series resistance, but mainly combining steady-state, transient and frequency-domain experiments in the same model can not only confirm the above mentioned publications but give additional insight with regards to the influence of mobile ions.

We measure the current-voltage (JV) curve, impedance spectroscopy in the dark and a voltage step response of a methylammonium lead iodide (MAPI) perovskite solar cell (details on cell structure in section 3). Our numerical simulation model ¹⁹ is fitted to the transient JV curve. The hysteresis is well reproduced quantitatively as shown in Figure 1a. The same parameter set is now used to simulate the impedance spectroscopy and the voltage step results. As shown in Figure 1b and Figure 1c the simulation does not reproduce the measurement results well.

Figure 1: Example of simulation mismatch. Measurement (black) and simulation (green) of a planar perovskite solar cell. a) JV curve with a ramp rate of 89 V/s. b) Impedance spectroscopy in the dark. c) Transient current as response to a voltage step from 0 volt to 1.5 volt at $t=0$. Despite the agreement of simulation and measurement in the JV curve, they do not match for impedance and voltage step experiments. Parameters extracted from JV curve fitting (a) are thus likely to be inaccurate.

The parameter set describing the JV curve with hysteresis well, does not match with the impedance spectroscopy results or the transient voltage step. The parameters are inaccurate and might be misinterpreted although the JV curve is reproduced.

In the past we have demonstrated parameter extraction of organic solar cells using numerical simulations^{20,21}. By fitting numerical simulations to measurement results for several experimental techniques the parameter correlation can be reduced significantly²⁰. Moreover, we have shown that a rather simple drift-diffusion model with constant charge mobilities, discrete traps and ohmic contacts is sufficient to simultaneously reproduce JV curve, photo-CELIV, OCVD, TPC, capacitance-voltage, impedance and intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy (IMPS) data for a bulk-heterojunction organic solar cell²¹.

In this publication we present various measurements and simulations of a planar MAPI perovskite solar cell. Our simulation model incorporating mobile ions and charge traps is capable of describing the hysteresis of JV curves with varied scan rates, the dependence of the open-circuit voltage on the light intensity, transient photocurrent, impedance spectroscopy in the dark and under illumination and IMPS. The main signatures observed in all these experimental techniques are reproduced by the simulation model using one single parameter set for all simulations.

To the best of our knowledge this is the most comprehensive description of the device physics of perovskite solar cells up to now. We show that the major physical effects observed in perovskite solar cells can consistently be described by a device model incorporating inert mobile ions and traps. Based on our model we investigate the influence of mobile ions, traps and other parameters on the experimental results. In the last section we show a parameter analysis to determine which factors limit the device performance.

3. Methods

3.1. Experimental Methods

All experiments were performed with the all-in-one measurement platform Paios 4.0 from Fluxim²². All experiments were computer-controlled and sequentially performed with minimal delay in order to minimize cell degradation between two measurements. A white LED (maximum intensity 500 W/cm²) was used as illumination source for all experiments. Eight nominally identical solar cells were characterized to test the reproducibility. The full data set of all measured curves is shown in the supporting information (SI).

3.2. Numerical Methods

The simulation model used in this study is implemented in the simulation software Setfos 4.6 from Fluxim¹⁹. The charge generation profile within the MAPI layer is calculated by the transfer matrix method using wavelength-dependent complex refractive indices of all layers.

Figure 2: Device layout and band-diagram of the simulated device.

Drift-diffusion calculations are performed within the three layers TaTm (p-doped hole transport layer), MAPI and C60 (n-doped electron transport layer) as shown in Figure 2. All model equations are shown in the supporting information (SI). Two mobile ionic species (one positive one negative) of the same density are allowed to move inside the MAPI layers. The interfaces to TaTm and C60 are treated as ion-blocking. In the MAPI layer 0.5 eV deep traps lead to Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination. SRH recombination is necessary to reproduce the ideality factor of approximately 2 as observed in the light-intensity dependence of the open-circuit voltage. An external series resistance is considered in the simulation accounting for the combined effect of the internal measurement resistor (50 Ohm) of the voltage source, the measurement resistor for current measurement (20 Ohm) and further parasitic resistances as for example in the TCO.

The impedance spectra and the intensity modulated photocurrent spectra (IMPS) are calculated from the Fourier transformation of a transient step response calculation as described by Ershov et al.²³.

We would like to stress the importance of taking the transport layers into account in such simulations. The voltage drop within the doped transport layers depends on their conductivity. The voltage drop inside the perovskite layer and the distribution of the mobile ions within the layer are consequently influenced by the contact layers^{24,25}. The ion densities at the TaTm-MAPI and the MAPI-C60 interfaces are much lower when contact layers are considered in the simulation.

We assume an equal density of iodine vacancies (cations) and methylammonium (MA) vacancies (anions) to be present in the device where the MA vacancies have a much lower mobility. We show in the SI that simulations with only iodine vacancies (cations) being mobile produce very similar results.

No direct interaction among ions is assumed and no interaction of ions with electrons, holes or traps takes place. The position of the ions however influences the electric field inside the device and thereby the charge transport.

3.3. Device Fabrication

The solar cells were fully vacuum processed using a previously reported protocol²⁶. Briefly, the devices (scheme in Figure 2) were deposited in a p-i-n configuration onto indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass slides. *N4,N4,N4'',N4''*-tetra([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-yl)-[1,1':4',1''-terphenyl]-4,4''-diamine (TaTm) was used as the hole transport material (HTM), either intrinsic or doped by co-sublimation with 2,2'-(perfluoronaphthalene-2,6-diylidene) dimalononitrile (F₆-TCNNQ). The fullerene C₆₀ was used as the electron transport material (ETM) both intrinsic or doped by co-sublimation with *N1,N4*-bis(tri-*p*-tolylphosphoranylidene)benzene-1,4-diamine (PhIm). The MAPI perovskite films were prepared by dual source vacuum deposition of the two starting compounds, CH₃NH₃I and PbI₂, in a high vacuum chamber. The final device structure was ITO/TaTm:F₆-TCNNQ (40 nm)/TaTm (10 nm)/MAPI (500 nm)/C₆₀ (10 nm)/C₆₀:PhIm (40 nm)/Ag (100 nm). The active cell area is 0.065 cm².

4. Results and Discussion

We perform measurements on perovskite solar cells, fabricated as described in the Section Device Fabrication. To test the reproducibility, 8 nominally identical devices were characterized. The results of all cells are shown in the SI. For the sake of better readability, we show only one representative device in the manuscript.

The simulation model as described in the section Numerical Methods is applied to simulate the same characterization techniques as in the measurements. The parameters of the model are adjusted to reach an agreement between simulation and measurement.

Figure 3 shows measurement and simulation data for nine distinct experiments. In Figure 3a-c JV curves measured by forward and reverse scan are shown. The scan rate is increased from a) to c). The short-circuit current of 10 mA/cm² is low since a white LED (500 W/cm²) is used for the illumination instead of a sun simulator. With scan rates below 1 V/s the hysteresis is very low. Only if very high scan rates up to 500 V/s are applied a pronounced hysteresis appears (Figure 3c). We simulate the same transient voltage ramp up and down to obtain a JV curve with hysteresis. At low scan rates the hysteresis is small in the simulation as well as in the measurement (Figure 3a). With higher scan rate a pronounced hysteresis appears in the measurement and is well reproduced by the simulation. Here we confirm that even hysteresis-free devices can have a hysteresis that is shifted to different time scales, consistent with the finding of Jacobs et al.¹⁸.

The dependence of the open-circuit voltage on the light intensity is shown in Figure 3d. Its ideality ($n_{id} = q / (k \cdot T) \cdot dV_{oc} / d(\ln(L))$) is clearly above 1.0 indicating dominant SRH recombination^{21,27,28}. In the simulation an ideality factor higher than 1.0 is only achievable with trap-assisted recombination. The simulation reproduces the dependence of the open-circuit voltage on the light intensity.

Figure 3: Measurement (black) and simulation (red) of the perovskite solar cell. a-c) JV curves with hysteresis and varied scan rates. The device is illuminated with a white LED. The short-circuit current is therefore lower compared to the short-circuit current under AM1.5. d) Dependence of the open-circuit voltage on the light intensity. e) Photocurrent as response to 2 subsequent light pulses. The first light pulse is from $-160 \mu\text{s}$ to $-50 \mu\text{s}$. The second light pulse from $0 \mu\text{s}$ to $100 \mu\text{s}$. f) Transient current as response to a voltage step in the dark in log-log representation. g) Impedance spectra in the dark in capacitance-frequency representation. h) Impedance spectra under illumination in capacitance-frequency representation. i) Intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy (IMPS).

Figure 3e shows the transient current response to two subsequent short light pulses. The measured current rise of the first pulse is significantly slower than the current rise of the second pulse. This behaviour is reproduced very well by the simulation using traps. During the first light pulse traps are being filled. In the subsequent pulse the traps are already filled, therefore the current rise is faster. If the delay time between the two pulses is increased to milliseconds the first and the second current rise are identical again. In this case all trapped charges are released during the delay time. Therefore, the double light pulse measurement is well suited to study trapping in perovskite solar cells. Due to the short pulse length of $100 \mu\text{s}$ this experiment is not sensitive to ion motion or accumulation (as long as the waiting time in the dark before the experiment is long enough).

In Figure 3f the transient current as response to a voltage step is shown. O’Kane et al. presented transient voltage step simulations on perovskite devices¹⁴. We use higher voltage steps than O’Kane which allows us to study charge injection as we detail in the following.

Figure 4: Simulation of a forward-bias voltage step from 0 to 1.5 V. a) Transient current. b and c) Charge carrier density profiles of electrons, holes, anions and cations at two different time steps as marked in a. The HTM-perovskite and perovskite-ETM interfaces are located at 50 nm and 550 nm, respectively.

The current peak before 1 μ s is the charging current of the device capacitance. Afterwards the current is small and then increases steeply at around 100 μ s. To illustrate the origin of this effect we plot the spatial charge carrier density profiles in Figure 4. The device is preconditioned at 0 volt where the built-in voltage drives the cations (assumed to be iodine vacancies) to the hole contact layer. A few microseconds after the voltage step to 1.5 volt is applied, the ions are still at their steady-state position (Figure 4b). The accumulated cations hinder hole injection due to the strong electric field at the interface. After 1 millisecond the cations have moved away from the interface (Figure 4c) enabling charge injection. Charges recombine in the bulk or at the opposite interface and a steady-state current flows. In the simulation (Figure 3 and Figure 4) the surface recombination is assumed to be very weak, corresponding to passivated, charge-selective contacts. Therefore, electrons can accumulate at the hole contact and holes can accumulate at the electron contact (Figure 4c). The steepness of the current rise after 100 μ s (Figure 4a) is influenced by the surface recombination. A comparison of a device with high and with low surface recombination is presented in the SI.

We conclude: Voltage step experiments are well suited to study the charge injection behaviour of perovskite solar cells. As we show in the SI a steep rise is an indication for low surface recombination.

Figure 3g shows the capacitance-frequency representation of an impedance measurement. The capacitance rise at low frequency (<100 Hz) is reproduced by the simulation. The transition frequency depends on the ion conductivity (ion density times the ion mobility). In Figure 5a simulation results with varied ion mobility are shown. The transition frequency of the capacitance varies with the mobility. Varying the ion density has the same effect. If ions are disabled in the simulation the capacitance remains low at low frequencies.

Figure 3h shows impedance spectroscopy data under illumination. Under illumination the capacitance at low frequencies reaches extraordinarily high values, consistent with what has been reported in literature⁵. In these experiments the word “capacitance” can be misleading. Moia and co-workers described the behaviour as an “ionic-to-electronic current amplification”²⁹. The idea behind this: The oscillating voltage moves the ions between the contacts. When ions are close to one contact injection is enhanced, if they are close to the other contact injection is suppressed. An increased injection enables a large electron-hole current to flow in phase with the modulated ions. The mobile ions only open the door for

electronic charges. Since the ion accumulation is out-of-phase with the voltage modulation, also the electronic current is out-of-phase and a very high apparent capacitance is observed. The higher the bulk conductivity, the higher the observed “capacitance”. Hence, the observed “capacitance” increases with illumination. Our simulation reproduces this effect and capacitance values of more than $1 \mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$ are reached at 1 Hz. The same mechanism is also well-explained by Jacobs et al. using numerical simulation¹⁸ and Pockett et al. using equivalent circuit modeling¹⁶. Furthermore its relation to hysteresis and voltage step response was recently discussed by Ebadi et al.³⁰. The magnitude of the capacitance as well as the frequency of the onset depend on the ion mobility as shown in Figure 5b. Without mobile ions the capacitance remains low.

Figure 3i shows intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy (IMPS) data. In this technique the light intensity is modulated and the current response is measured^{21,31,32}. The peak of the imaginary part of the IMPS signal is often attributed to a charge transport time²¹. In perovskite solar cells the second peak or shoulder at low frequency is of special interest. Several groups observed a peak at low frequencies and speculated that mobile ions could be the cause^{16,33}. Our measurement shows a shoulder rather than a peak in a similar frequency range. The IMPS simulation reproduces this peak. We can therefore confirm the hypothesis that mobile ions are responsible for the low-frequency peak. The frequency of the peak depends on the ion mobility as shown in Figure 5c. Without mobile ions the peak vanishes. To the best of our knowledge this is the first published drift-diffusion simulation of IMPS including mobile ions.

We conclude: The three experiments in the frequency domain are well suited to study ion conductivity.

Figure 5: Simulation results with varied ion mobility and disabled ions (dashed line). a) Impedance spectroscopy in the dark. b) Impedance spectroscopy under illumination. c) Intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy (IMPS).

The plots in Figure 3 have been obtained using a manual fitting procedure as outlined in our previous publication²¹. Some parameters are assumed to be known (active area, layer thickness), some are taken from literature (permittivity) or can be directly analysed (series resistance). Starting with "realistic" parameters for mobilities, recombination efficiency, energy levels, ion and trapping values we then obtained initial results, which were manually fitted after "inspection by eye". For this the criterium was that specific features like a rise or peak were reproduced at a correct timescale and magnitude. Table 1 and Table 2 show the resulting material and device parameters obtained from the fit and used in all simulations shown in Figure 3. We want to stress again that the parameter set was identical for every simulation and only the operating condition, modelling the characterization technique, was varied.

Parameter	HTM, TaTm	MAPI	ETM, C60
Thickness	50 nm (measured)	500 nm (measured)	50 nm (measured)
Electron mobility	-	0.2 cm ² /Vs	8.9e-4 cm ² /Vs
Hole mobility	1.5e-3 cm ² /Vs	0.1 cm ² /Vs	-
Recombination constant	-	1e-10 cm ³ /s	-
Relative Permittivity	3 (literature ³⁴)	35 (literature ³⁵)	3.9 (literature ³⁴)
HOMO energy	5.38 eV	5.44 eV	5.77 eV
LUMO energy	3.59 eV	3.82 eV	3.85 eV
Electron trap density	-	1.2e16 cm ⁻³	-
Electron trap depth	-	0.5 eV (literature ³⁶)	-
Electron trap electron capture rate	-	3e-10 cm ³ /s	-
Electron trap hole capture rate	-	3e-12 cm ³ /s	-
n-doping density	-	-	1.5e18 cm ⁻³
p-doping density	7e18 cm ⁻³	-	-
Mobile cation density	-	5e17 cm ⁻³	-
Mobile anion density	-	5e17 cm ⁻³	-
Cation mobility	-	5e-8 cm ² /Vs	-
Anion mobility	-	1e-14 cm ² /Vs	-
Effective density of states	1e27 m ⁻³	6e25 m ⁻³	1e27 m ⁻³

Table 1: Layer-dependent simulation parameters used for all simulations in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Parameter	Value
External series resistance	25 Ohm (analysed)
Device area	0.065 cm ² (measured)
Temperature	293 K (measured)
Boundary condition top electrode hole-density	6.8e18 cm ⁻³
Boundary condition bottom electrode electron-density	6.5e17 cm ⁻³

Table 2: Layer-independent simulation parameters used for all simulations in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5.

We present a numerical device model for perovskite solar cells that is capable to describe consistently all major effects found in a variety of opto-electrical experiments. The electron and hole mobilities of the perovskite layer are 0.2 cm²/Vs and 0.1 cm²/Vs, respectively. This is at the lower end of published mobilities for polycrystalline MAPI perovskites (0.1 – 25 cm²/Vs³⁷). In our drift-diffusion model the charge carrier mobility is an effective macroscopic quantity of the layer including grain boundaries. The low bulk mobility might be explained by the rather small crystals (~100 nm²⁶) of our perovskite solar cells. The recombination coefficient of 1·10⁻¹⁰ cm³/s lies in the expected range (1·10⁻⁹ to 1·10⁻¹⁰ cm³/s³⁸). The contact properties show ohmic injection in agreement with previous results on the same stack²⁶. The trap depth of 0.5 eV was chosen according to results of Baumann et al. from thermally stimulated currents³⁶.

Governing physical effects

When mobile ions accumulate at an interface with a transport layer (HTM or ETM), the charge injection property of this interface is altered. With applied voltage ions migrate from one interface towards the other. These two effects cause the JV curve hysteresis (Figure 3a-c), the high capacitance at low frequencies under illumination (Figure 3h) and the delayed current-rise in the voltage pulse experiments (Figure 3f).

The simulation results of Figure 3 are very sensitive to the doping density of the boundary layers TaTm and C60. If the contact layers are highly conductive most of the potential drops within the perovskite layer²⁴. Ions compensate this voltage drop when they move to the interfaces. The JV curve hysteresis does therefore most probably also depend on the conductivity of the boundary layers. A high conductivity would lead to a higher potential drop inside the bulk and therefore to a more pronounced JV curve hysteresis.

In solar cells with small built-in fields surface recombination plays an important role. Due to the low electric field charges may reach the opposite contact and recombine there. A passivated contact can hinder such recombination. In our material system the interface recombination is suppressed in a similar way as it is done in highly efficient OLED stacks³⁹. The addition of 10 nm of intrinsic transport layer material on both sides leads to an effectively suppressed surface recombination²⁶. Omitting these thin intrinsic passivation layers alters the voltage step response as discussed in the SI. Our model results are consistent: Decent agreement between simulation and measurement is only reached with a low surface recombination.

We have shown in a previous publication that even in the presence of mobile ions the JV curve hysteresis vanishes if the surface recombination is sufficiently low and the diffusion length is sufficiently high⁴⁰. In the present case the contacts are passivated, minimizing surface recombination. The JV curve hysteresis observed at faster scan rates can therefore be related to a relatively short diffusion length leading to high bulk recombination of charge carriers. In the SI we show that improving the bulk-quality (lower SRH recombination and higher charge carrier mobility) reduces the hysteresis significantly.

The order of magnitude of the high capacitance under illumination is reproduced by the simulation. However, the simulation always shows a distinct capacitance plateau for low frequencies, while the measurements often show a steady rise. A possible explanation is dispersive ion motion. While in our model we assume a constant and homogeneous ion mobility, this may not hold in real perovskite layers where e.g. due to grain boundaries ion transport may in fact be dispersive²⁹. In a simple picture, a unique ion mobility gives rise to one characteristic frequency in the impedance (as well as IMPS) experiment, while a distribution of mobilities should lead to a “smeared-out” transition and therefore a continued rise of the capacitance.

Reverse voltage step

To complement the set of experiments shown in Figure 3 we perform an additional experiment: A voltage step from forward to reverse. Figure 6 shows the measurement and simulation of a voltage step from +3 volt to -3 volt. In this case the simulation fails to describe the measurement.

Figure 6: Measurement and simulation result of a MAPI perovskite solar cell. A voltage step to +3 volt is applied for 300 ms. At $t=0$ the voltage is changed to -3 volt. The current response is shown. The simulation fails to describe the measured current.

In the measurement a reverse current is observed starting at 3 milliseconds and vanishing after 1 second. The simulated current shows a time-of-flight (TOF)^{41,42} behaviour. The ions are preconditioned in forward direction. Most of the iodine vacancies accumulate within the first nanometres close to the ETM interface. When the voltage is reversed these ions migrate through the bulk until they reach the HTM interface. The ion movement leads to a drift current of around 0.2 mA/cm². When the interface is reached after the transit time of 3 milliseconds the current goes to zero in the simulation. At this point the additional current peak, observed in the measurement, starts. The integrated current density results in a sheet charge density of $4.4 \cdot 10^{13}$ cm⁻². If the assumed ion density of $5 \cdot 10^{17}$ cm⁻³ is integrated over the MAPI thickness a comparable sheet charge of $2.5 \cdot 10^{13}$ cm⁻² is obtained. We therefore speculate that a chemical reaction occurs at one of the interfaces leading to a reduction or oxidation of the contact material induced by the mobile ions. This effect does not occur in MAPI perovskite solar cells with TiO₂ and Spiro-OMeTAD contact layers, therefore it seems to be dependent on the choice of contact material. Alternatively, reverse injection may be responsible for this transient current. The effect deserves further investigation and the simulation model may need to be adapted accordingly.

Model limitations

In this section we discuss further possible model limitations.

- In the presented model the interfaces between layers are sharp and the layers are homogeneous. The devices studied here show an interface roughness of about 10 nm²⁶.
- In our model two mobile ion species (positive and negative) are used. In reality there may be more than two active species^{43,44}. In the SI we show that a model with only one mobile species and a second, immobile species produces very similar effects.
- We use constant mobilities for the migration of ions. In reality ion migration may be field dependent and dispersive. Furthermore, Shao et al. showed that ions migrate preferably along grain boundaries⁴⁵. In such a case two mobilities for the same ion

type might be required for its description: A bulk ion mobility and an ion mobility along the grain boundaries.

- We do not impose an upper limit on the local ion concentration at the layer boundaries. This is a subject of our ongoing investigations and will be discussed elsewhere.

Parameter Study

On the basis of the simulation results we perform steady-state JV curve simulations. This allows us to assess the influence of specific parameters on the power conversion efficiency. The power conversion efficiency and the fill-factor are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Parameter variation on the basis of the simulation results of Table 1 and Table 2. a) Power conversion efficiency improvement for different parameter variations. b) Fill-factor for different parameter variations.

A doping density of 10^{19} cm^{-3} in both transport layers improves the charge carrier extraction at the contacts and leads to a higher fill-factor. The resistive losses in the ETM and HTM are however not limiting the performance. Using 10 times higher electron and hole mobilities does not improve the performance.

A smaller density of mobile ions (10% compared to the base simulation) leads only to a minor device improvement of 3.3%. The mobile ions are not a major obstacle for efficient device operation if the charge carrier mobility is high enough and the surface recombination is low enough⁴⁰. Reducing the trap density to 10% of the base simulation leads to a large improvement by 14% due to reduced SRH-recombination. A similar improvement is reached for 10 times higher electron and hole mobilities in the perovskite material leading to better charge extraction. The external series resistance as caused by the lateral conductivity of the TCO can reduce the performance significantly⁴⁶. Reducing it to zero leads to an improvement of only 2% in our case. With all the effects combined a relative performance improvement of 23% is obtained. The improvement stems mainly from a higher fill-factor (Figure 7b). Further performance improvements could be achieved by optimized light management².

5. Conclusions

We performed a variety of characterization experiments with vacuum deposited methylammonium lead iodide perovskite solar cells, including JV curves with different scan rates, light-intensity dependent open-circuit voltage, impedance spectroscopy, intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy (IMPS), transient photocurrents and transient voltage steps.

We developed a multi-layer drift-diffusion simulation model incorporating mobile ions to simulate all experimental techniques. A decent agreement between simulation and measurement is reached for all techniques using only one parameter set in the simulation. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study presenting a consistent device model that is capable to simultaneously describe transient, steady-state and frequency-dependent experimental results of perovskite solar cells.

Our study shows that it is necessary to consider mobile ions and Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination in the simulation to reproduce experimental results. Whether one, two or even more different mobile ionic species are incorporated does not play a major role for reproducing the experimental results by simulation. Further model complexity like ferroelectricity or considering individual grain boundaries is not required to understand and describe the device physics of perovskite cells.

As the physical processes in perovskite solar cells are complex, an approach combining different experimental techniques is required to achieve consistent, accurate and reliable results. We show a possible path to reach this goal and discuss the limitations of this approach. Using the device model with the derived parameters allows us to study different approaches to improve the cell performance.

The delayed current peak resulting from a voltage step to a negative voltage can however not be reproduced with the drift-diffusion model. We speculate that either reverse injection or a reversible redox reaction of ions with the contact layer material may be responsible for this effect. Further effort is required to extend the device model accordingly.

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7. Supporting Information

Physical Model; Model Parameter Analysis – Simulation results with none, one or two mobile ion species; Voltage Pulse – Influence of surface recombination; IV-Curve Hysteresis; All Measurement Data

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Supporting Information: Consistent Device Simulation Model Describing Perovskite Solar Cells in Steady-State, Transient and Frequency Domain

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1. Physical Model

1.1. Model Equations

In this section the governing equations of the drift-diffusion model implemented in Setfos 4.6¹ are explained. The quantities are described in the next section.

1.1.1. Electronic Drift-Diffusion

The continuity equations for electrons and holes govern the change in charge carrier density due to current flow, electron or hole exchange with traps, recombination and generation.

$$\frac{\partial n_e}{\partial t}(x, t) = \frac{1}{q} \cdot \frac{\partial j_e}{\partial x}(x, t) - R_{te}(x, t) - R(x, t) + G_{opt} \cdot g(x) \quad \text{Eq. 1a}$$

$$\frac{\partial n_h}{\partial t}(x, t) = -\frac{1}{q} \cdot \frac{\partial j_h}{\partial x}(x, t) - R_{th}(x, t) - R(x, t) + G_{opt} \cdot g(x) \quad \text{Eq. 1b}$$

For the calculation of the charge generation profile $g(x)$ Setfos considers the measured illumination spectrum, the complex refractive indices and the thickness of each layer of the cell stack.

Radiative recombination is described by

$$R(x, t) = \beta \cdot n_e(x, t) \cdot n_h(x, t) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The currents of electrons and holes consist of drift in the electric field and diffusion due to the charge carrier density gradients. Hereby the absolute unit charge $q=1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{C}$ and the sign convention for the current according to Selberherr² are used.

$$j_e(x, t) = n_e(x, t) \cdot q \cdot \mu_e \cdot E(x, t) + \mu_e \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot \frac{\partial n_e}{\partial x}(x, t) \quad \text{Eq. 3a}$$

$$j_h(x, t) = n_h(x, t) \cdot q \cdot \mu_h \cdot E(x, t) - \mu_h \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot \frac{\partial n_h}{\partial x}(x, t) \quad \text{Eq. 3b}$$

1.1.2. Ionic Drift-Diffusion

The continuity equation for anions and cations governs the change in ion density due to ionic current flow.

$$\frac{\partial n_a}{\partial t}(x, t) = \frac{1}{q} \cdot \frac{\partial j_a}{\partial x}(x, t) \quad \text{Eq. 4a}$$

$$\frac{\partial n_c}{\partial t}(x, t) = -\frac{1}{q} \cdot \frac{\partial j_c}{\partial x}(x, t) \quad \text{Eq. 4b}$$

Ions diffuse due to a density gradient or drift in the electric field.

$$j_a(x, t) = n_a(x, t) \cdot q \cdot \mu_a \cdot E(x, t) + \mu_a \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot \frac{\partial n_a}{\partial x}(x, t) \quad \text{Eq. 5a}$$

$$j_c(x, t) = n_c(x, t) \cdot q \cdot \mu_c \cdot E(x, t) - \mu_c \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot \frac{\partial n_c}{\partial x}(x, t) \quad \text{Eq. 5b}$$

The continuity and drift-diffusion equations for negatively/positively charged ions are thus equivalent to the ones for electrons and holes, except that the ions cannot leave the perovskite layer and generation/recombination is excluded.

1.1.3. Total Current, Poisson and Device Voltage

The total current is the sum of electron current, hole current, anion current, cation current, displacement current and the current through the parallel resistance. This total current is constant in x .

$$j(x, t) = j_e(x, t) + j_h(x, t) + j_a(x, t) + j_c(x, t) + \frac{\partial E}{\partial t}(x, t) \cdot \varepsilon + \frac{V_{dev}(t)}{R_p} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

The Poisson equation relates the electric field with the charges inside the layer.

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial x}(x, t) = -\frac{q}{\varepsilon} \cdot [n_h(x, t) - n_e(x, t) + n_c(x, t) - n_a(x, t) + n_{t,h}(x, t) - n_{t,e}(x, t) + n_{p-doping}(x) - n_{n-doping}(x)] \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

The integral of the electric field over position x plus the built-in voltage is called device voltage. It is the applied voltage minus the voltage drop over the series resistance³.

$$V_{dev}(t) = \int_0^d E(x, t) \cdot dx + V_{bi} = V_{applied}(t) - R_S \cdot j(t) \cdot S \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

1.1.4. The Built-In Voltage

The built-in voltage is defined as the difference in workfunctions of the electrodes. The workfunctions are calculated using the boundary charge carrier densities n_{h0} and n_{e0} .

$$V_{bi} = \frac{\phi_A - \phi_C}{q} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$\phi_C = E_{LUMO} - \ln\left(\frac{n_{e0}}{N_0}\right) \cdot k_B \cdot T \quad \text{Eq. 10a}$$

$$\phi_A = E_{HOMO} + \ln\left(\frac{n_{h0}}{N_0}\right) \cdot k_B \cdot T \quad \text{Eq. 10b}$$

1.1.5. Boundary Conditions

As boundary conditions the electron density at the anode and the hole density at the cathode are set to fixed values n_{e0} and n_{h0} .

$$n_h(0, t) = n_{h0} \quad \text{Eq. 11a}$$

$$n_e(0, t) = N_0^2 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_g}{k_B \cdot T}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{n_{h0}} \quad \text{Eq. 11b}$$

$$n_e(d, t) = n_{e0} \quad \text{Eq. 11c}$$

$$n_h(d, t) = N_0^2 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_g}{k_B \cdot T}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{n_{e0}} \quad \text{Eq. 11d}$$

The electric potential is evaluated according to

$$\varphi(x, t) = \int_0^x E(x', t) \cdot dx' \quad \text{Eq. 12a}$$

$$\varphi(0, t) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 12b}$$

$$\varphi(d, t) = V_{dev}(t) - V_{bi}(t) \quad \text{Eq. 12c}$$

As ions cannot leave the perovskite layer the ionic current is set to zero at the interface HTM-MAPI (position d_1) and at the interface MAPI-ETM (position d_2).

$$j_a(d_1, t) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 13a}$$

$$j_c(d_1, t) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 13b}$$

$$j_a(d_2, t) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 13c}$$

$$j_c(d_2, t) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 13d}$$

The total ion density is the integral over the perovskite layer.

$$N_a = \frac{1}{d} \cdot \int_0^d n_a(x, t) \cdot dx \quad \text{Eq. 14a}$$

$$N_c = \frac{1}{d} \cdot \int_0^d n_c(x, t) \cdot dx \quad \text{Eq. 14b}$$

1.1.6. Trapping

Trapping and de-trapping of electron traps is described by the electron trap continuity equation. The electron trap can either exchange electrons with the LUMO level at the rate R_{te} or exchange holes with the HOMO level at the rate R_{th} .

$$\frac{\partial n_t}{\partial t} = R_{te} - R_{th} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

Free electrons in the LUMO can be captured by traps. Trapped electrons can be released thermally activated into the LUMO.

$$R_{te} = c_e \cdot n_e \cdot (N_t - n_t) - c_e \cdot N_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_t - E_{LUMO}}{k_B \cdot T}\right) \cdot n_t \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

Trapped electrons can recombine with a free hole. An empty trap can capture an electron from the HOMO level by thermal activation (leaving behind a hole).

$$R_{th} = c_h \cdot n_h \cdot n_t - c_h \cdot N_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_t - E_{HOMO}}{k_B \cdot T}\right) \cdot (N_t - n_t) \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

The three equations above describe SRH-recombination in a two-step process. Free electrons are captured in the trap and subsequently recombine with a free hole. Alternatively, an electron can be thermally activated from the HOMO to the trap level and from the trap level to the LUMO. The latter two routes occur however with lower probability.

1.2. Physical Quantities

Quantity	Quantity	Unit
n_e	Electron density	cm^{-3}
n_h	Hole density	cm^{-3}
n_c	Cation density	cm^{-3}
n_a	Anion density	cm^{-3}
$n_{t,e}$	Density of trapped electrons	cm^{-3}
$n_{t,h}$	Density of trapped holes	cm^{-3}
$n_{n\text{-doping}}$	n-type doping density	cm^{-3}
$n_{p\text{-doping}}$	p-type doping density	cm^{-3}
j_e	Electron current	mA/cm^2
j_h	Hole current	mA/cm^2
j_c	Cation current	mA/cm^2
j_a	Anion current	mA/cm^2
j	Total current	mA/cm^2
E	Electric field	V/m
φ	Electric potential	V
R	Recombination rate	$\text{s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$
R_{te}	Electron trap – electron exchange rate	$\text{s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$
R_{th}	Electron trap – hole exchange rate	$\text{s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$
$g(x)$	Charge generation profile	$\text{s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-3}$
x	Dimension in layer direction	nm
t	Time	s
d	Full simulation domain width	nm
d_1	Position of the interface HTM-MAPI	nm
d_2	Position of the interface MAPI-ETM	nm
S	Device area	cm^2
μ_e	Electron mobility	cm^2/Vs
μ_h	Hole mobility	cm^2/Vs
μ_c	Cation mobility	cm^2/Vs
μ_a	Anion mobility	cm^2/Vs
β	Recombination coefficient	cm^3/s
V_{source}	Voltage of the voltage source that is connected to the device	V
V_{bi}	Built-in voltage	V
R_s	Series resistance	Ω
R_p	Parallel resistance	Ω
Φ_A	Workfunction of the anode	eV
Φ_C	Workfunction of the cathode	eV
E_{HOMO}	Energy of highest occupied molecular orbital	eV
E_{LUMO}	Energy of lowest unoccupied molecular orbital	eV
E_t	Trap energy	eV
n_{e0}	Electron density at the right electrode ($x=d$) as boundary condition of the simulation.	cm^{-3}
n_{h0}	Hole density at the left electrode ($x=0$) as boundary condition of the simulation.	cm^{-3}
N_0	Density of chargeable sites	cm^{-3}
N_t	Trap density	cm^{-3}
N_c	Total cation density	cm^{-2}
N_a	Total anion density	cm^{-2}
c_e	Capture rate for electrons	cm^3/s
c_h	Capture rate for holes	cm^3/s
G_{opt}	Photon-to-charge conversion efficiency	1

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	This factor accounts for non-dissociated excitons.	
ϵ	Electrical permittivity ($\epsilon = \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_r$)	F/m
q	Unit charge	C
k_B	Boltzmann constant	J/K
T	Temperature	K

Table S1: Physical quantities used in the equations of the previous section and in the main text.

2. Model Parameter Analysis

2.1. Simulation Results with and without Mobile Ions

Figure S1: Comparison of simulation with (red) and without (blue) mobile ions. The measurement is shown in black. (a-i) The figure type is identical to Figure 3 a-i in the manuscript.

Figure S1 shows the comparison of the simulation result with and without mobile ions. From Figure S1c it is evident that the JV-curve hysteresis only occurs in the presence of mobile ions in our model.

The slow current-rise observed in the double light pulse (Figure S1e) caused by slow trapping disappears without mobile ions. The mobile ions do not move on these time-scales, but their accumulation at the interface in steady-state lowers the effective field in the device. In the case without the mobile ions the trap-filling is still a slow process, but the current can rise fast enough due to the high built-in field. The characteristic current-rise in Figure S1f disappears without mobile ions. Charges can be injected from the very beginning of the voltage step.

The low frequency effects in impedance spectroscopy (Figure S1g and Figure S1h) disappear when ions are disabled. The same is true for the low frequency shoulder in IMPS in Figure S1i.

2.2. Simulation Results with one Mobile Ionic Specie

Figure S2: Comparison of simulation with two mobile ionic species (red) and with one mobile ionic species (blue). The measurement is shown in black. (a-i) The figure type is identical to Figure 3 a-i in the manuscript.

There are several ionic species moving inside a methylammonium perovskite solar cell. There is convincing evidence, that iodine vacancies (positively charged) are mobile⁴⁻⁶. There is evidence that methylammonium vacancies (negatively charged) are mobile too but have a much lower mobility⁶⁻⁸. Numerical simulations with mobile ions have been performed with one species mobile and one species immobile⁹⁻¹¹ as well as with two mobile species¹²⁻¹⁴. Figure S2 shows a comparison between those two simulations. The red curve is the same as in the manuscript using two mobile species. The blue line is the simulation result using one mobile type (positively charged iodine vacancies). In this case the negatively charged MA vacancies of the same density are modelled as homogeneously distributed fixed space charge (doping).

Interestingly, the results of the two simulations look almost identical. Apart from the rise-time in the transient voltage step experiment (Figure S2f), all major effects are also observed if only one ion type is mobile.

We conclude that, as long as the mobility of the MA ions is very low, it is not of great importance to the simulation result whether one or two mobile ionic species are considered.

2.3. Simulation Results with and without Traps

Figure S3: Comparison of simulation with trapping (red) and without trapping (blue). The measurement is shown in black. (a-i) The figure type is identical to Figure 3 a-i in the manuscript.

Figure S3 shows the comparison between simulation with traps and Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination and without traps.

Without traps and without SRH-recombination the fill factor is increased (Figure S3a), the ideality factor is close to 1.0 (Figure S3d). Without SRH-recombination the measurement results cannot be reproduced.

If trapping is disabled in the simulation the current-rise in the double light pulse experiment (Figure S3e) is faster. Both the first and the second response look identical. All other experiments in Figure S3 are only marginally influenced by trapping and SRH-recombination.

3. Voltage Pulse – Influence of Surface Recombination

The shape of the current-rise as response to a voltage step depends critically on the surface recombination. Figure S4a shows the simulation result of the perovskite solar cell of the manuscript (blue line). In this case the surface recombination is very low. The green line shows the simulation result with a high surface recombination. The rise-time is significantly slower compared to the case with passivated surfaces.

Surface recombination is modelled by a thin layer close to the interface where the recombination pre-factor is much larger than in the bulk.

To further investigate this effect, we fabricated devices with and without a 10 nm thick intrinsic passivation layer between perovskite and the doped ETL and HTL, respectively. These extra layers are expected to suppress surface recombination¹⁵. Voltage-step measurements on devices with and without these passivation layers are shown in Figure S4b. The current rise of the device without passivation layers is much slower. This behaviour is consistent with the simulation with a high surface recombination.

We conclude that a steep current-rise in the voltage step experiment is an indicator for well passivated surfaces.

Figure S4: Transient current as response to a voltage step. a) Numerical simulation with varied surface recombination. b) Measurement of two different MAPI perovskite solar cells.

4. JV-Curve Hysteresis

Even in the presence of mobile ions a perovskite solar cell can be hysteresis-free¹¹. In our previous publication we showed that a sufficiently high charge carrier lifetime in combination with a low surface recombination is required for a minimal hysteresis¹⁶.

The device under investigation has a good surface quality (low surface recombination) but a low bulk quality (low charge carrier lifetime). The simulated JV-curve with hysteresis is shown in Figure S5b.

In Figure S5a a device with low bulk quality and lower surface quality is shown. Here the hysteresis is the largest. Figure S5c shows a device with a high bulk quality but a low surface quality. A pronounced hysteresis is observed. Only in the case with high bulk and surface quality the hysteresis is minimal as shown in Figure S5d.

If the surface recombination is low (high surface quality) and the charge carrier lifetime is high (high bulk quality) then charges can be extracted even against the electric field created by the mobile ions¹⁶.

Figure S5: Simulations of JV-curves with hysteresis for different combinations of low (a,b) and high (c,d) bulk qualities and low (a,c) and high (b,d) surface qualities. A ramp-rate of 16 V/s has been used.

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5. All Measurement Data

Figure S6: Measurements of 5 nominally identical devices. (a-i) The figure type is identical to Figure 3 a-i in the manuscript.

Figure S6 shows the measurement data of 5 nominally identical devices. In total 8 devices were measured. Three devices did not work reliably therefore only 5 devices are shown here. The reproducibility of the devices is very good.

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